

PATELLA FRACTURES ORIF

To EVERT OR NOT TO EVERT?

Perfect reduction of the anterior cortex may or may not lead to perfect joint surface reduction. Joint reduction under visual control has been proposed.

D. Santos, A. Gavagnin, A. Fernández / Comments: D. Hoentzsch, R. Babst, F. Beeres, B. Link

May 2020

doi: 10.5281/zenodo.3863011

PRE

POST OP

Perfect reduction of the anterior patella surface may or may not lead to perfect joint surface reduction.

NOT
EVERTED
CASE

ID: 34-CO-608 / 70y
Case example 0: Not everted case

PRE X-ray

PRE CT

POST OP CT

Perfect reduction of the anterior patella surface
may or may not lead to perfect joint surface reduction.

PRE

POST OP

Perfect reduction
of the joint surface

Perfect reduction
of the anterior surface

EVERTED
CASE

ID: 34-CO-236 / 70y
Case 3 of 13

PRE X-ray

PRE CT

POST OP CT

Perfect reduction of the joint was achieved under direct visual control.

Perfect joint surface reduction is accepted to be important in patella ORIF.

Perfect reduction of the anterior patella surface may or may not lead to perfect joint surface reduction.

This may be more important in comminuted fractures.

Joint surface reduction under visual control either by lateral (1) or medial (2) arthrotomy has been proposed as a tool to handle this problem.

(1) <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/27441934>

(2) <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/10.1177/2309499017719378>

Most surgeons imagine patella fractures as a simple transverse fracture.

Most surgeons feel tension band is the way to handle most patella fractures.

AO SURGERY REFERENCE

Tension band wiring

Main indications
All displaced frontal/coronal (transverse) fractures
[Read full indications >](#)

Skill level
● ● ○

Equipment
● ● ○

Tension band stitch

Main indications
All displaced frontal/coronal (transverse) fractures in elderly osteoporotic patients
[Read full indications >](#)

Skill level
● ● ○

Equipment
● ● ○

Most surgeons imagine patella fractures as a simple transverse fracture, but our review of:

30 consecutive patella cases at the ICUC database showed a different picture

TRANSVERSE

1

COMPLEX

21

VERTICAL

3

3 excluded (no CT info)
2 referred cases (with previous osteosynthesis)
 $30 - 2 - 3 = 25$

**We present a trailer of the 13 consecutive, unselected,
HD documented cases included in the ICUC[®] database:**

PRE

Lateral parapatellar approach

0w

51w

ICUC Score Functional Limitation: 1 ▲ (0-4) - Pain: 1 ▲ (0-4)

Full weight bearing

PRE

0w

94w

Medial parapatellar approach

ICUC Score Functional Limitation: 2 ● (0-4) - Pain: 1 ▲ (0-4)

Full weight bearing

PRE

0w

Medial parapatellar approach

94w

Medial parapatellar approach

0w

PRE

52w

ICUC Score Functional Limitation: 0 (0-4) - Pain: 0 (0-4)

0 (0-4)

Full weight bearing

PRE

0w

8lw

Lateral parapatellar approach

ICUC Score Functional Limitation: **1** ▲ (0-4) - Pain: **0** (0-4)

Full weight bearing

Lateral parapatellar approach

0w

PRE

51w

ICUC Score Functional Limitation: 0

(0-4) - Pain: 1 ▲ (0-4)

Full weight bearing

PRE

0w

Lateral parapatellar approach

8w

PRE

0w

Lateral parapatellar approach

53w

Der

Lateral parapatellar approach

0w

PRE

48w wire removal

128w wire removal

187w from 1st surgery

Lateral parapatellar approach

0w

PRE

27w

ICUC Score Functional Limitation: 2 ▲ (0-4) - Pain: 1 ▲ (0-4)

Full weight bearing

Medial parapatellar approach

0w

PRE

23w

Straight midline incision through the wound

0w

PRE

16w

ICUC Score Functional Limitation: 1 ▲ (0-4) - Pain: 1 ▲ (0-4)

Full weight bearing

PRE

Straight midline incision

0w

ICUC Score

Functional Limitation:

No info

-

Pain: No info

Full weight bearing

Perfect joint surface reduction is accepted to be important in patella ORIF.

Perfect reduction of the anterior patella surface may or may not lead to perfect joint surface reduction.

Joint surface reduction under visual control either by lateral (1) or medial (2) arthrotomy has been proposed as a tool to handle this problem.

We include images from 13 consecutive cases of Patella ORIF from the ICUC database where eversion was used.

Links to 3D interactive colored models:

Case study 0
ID: 34-CO-608 / 70y

Case study 3 of 13
ID: 34-CO-236 / 70y

Case study 1 of 13
ID: 34-CO-087 / 50y

(1) <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/27441934>

(2) <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/10.1177/2309499017719378>

PATELLA FRACTURES ORIF

TO EVERT OR NOT TO EVERT?

Perfect reduction of the anterior cortex may or may not lead to perfect joint surface reduction. Joint reduction under visual control has been proposed.

EXPERT'S FEEDBACK:

Dankward Hoentzsch

May 2020

"I have underlined, that the eversion of the patella in patella fractures operative treatment is a key:

- to see the joint surface and fragments*
- to reduce them properly with the lowest footprints*
- create a joint surface in simple cases perfect and in complex fractures as good as possible*
- all these points are independent of the following osteosynthesis!*
- all regular osteosynthesis are possible and easier.*
- if an osteosynthesis is easier to achieve, the final result from non and high experienced surgeons are better*
- the procedure is faster and less "try and error"*
- the x-ray load might be lower because you have not to control the different steps with the imagine intensifier,*
- only the final documentation is needed*
- in all other joint fractures a good sight to the joint surface is the goal and in the different joints "state of the art"*
- I do not understand why the surgeons are so rigid and reserved to follow these rules.*
- I see too much bad osteosynthesis with the treatment of patella fractures. It is not an exotic problem but very often problem and demands a solution.*

How can we promote the eversion of the patella fracture?

We learned this from David Helfet and Dean Lorange and we want to acknowledge it."

Reto Babst

March 2020

“This are very instructive cases, which show the importance to treat patella fractures like other articular fractures with anatomic reduction and inter-fragmentary compression using lag screws supported by tension banding through the cannulated screw, which help to neutralise the tension in addition. The Lorch paper describes also the cerclage from the inside, which helps to reduce especially multifragmented patella fractures especially of the infra-patellar pole region.

This information needs to be spread, and ICUC is a good medium to do so.”

Frank Beerres

March 2020

“Great cases. They underline the superb platform to share knowledge.

I fully agree: either evert or arthrotomy. Personally I prefer these above the scope in order to anatomically reduce the fracture.”

Björn Link

March 2020

“Eversion is definitely recommended for complex patella fractures. These cases and the way they are presented splendidly illustrate the fact. However, simple fractures may as well be addressed arthroscopically.”

Reto Babst

March 2020

“This are very instructive cases, which show the importance to treat patella fractures like other articular fractures with anatomic reduction and inter-fragmentary compression using lag screws supported by tension banding through the cannulated screw, which help to neutralise the tension in addition. The Lorch paper describes also the cerclage from the inside, which helps to reduce especially multifragmented patella fractures especially of the infra-patellar pole region.

This information needs to be spread, and ICUC is a good medium to do so.”

FURTHER READINGS

1. LOW PROFILE MESH PLATING FOR PATELLA FRACTURES: VIDEO OF A NOVEL SURGICAL TECHNIQUE.
DIEDERIK O VERBEEK 1, LINDSAY E HICKERSON, STEPHEN J WARNER, DAVID L HELFET, DEAN G LORICH
<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/27441934>
2. SURGERY OF PATELLAR FRACTURES USING A MEDIAL PARAPATELLAR APPROACH.
YONG-CHEOL YOON, JAE-ANG SIM, JIN-HUN HONG
<https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/10.1177/2309499017719378>
3. TENSION BAND WIRING
<HTTPS://SURGERYREFERENCE.AOFOUNDATION.ORG/ORTHOPEDIC-TRAUMA/ADULT-TRAUMA/PATELLA/COMPLETE-ARTICULAR-FRONTAL-CORONAL-SIMPLE-FRACTURE-OF-THE-DISTAL-THIRD/TENSION-BAND-WIRING#PRINCIPLES>
4. EFFECT OF COMPUTERIZED TOMOGRAPHY ON CLASSIFICATION AND TREATMENT PLAN FOR PATELLAR FRACTURES.
LAZARO, LIONEL E. MD*; WELLMAN, DAVID S. MD*; PARDEE, NADINE C. BA*; GARDNER, MICHAEL J. MD‡; TORO, JOSE B. MD‡; MACINTYRE, NEIL R. III MD*;
HELFET, DAVID L. MD*; LORICH, DEAN G. MD*
HTTPS://JOURNALS.LWW.COM/JORTHOTRAUMA/ABSTRACT/2013/06000/EFFECT_OF_COMPUTERIZED_TOMOGRAPHY_ON.8.ASPX
5. MULTIPLANAR FIXATION FOR PATELLA FRACTURES USING A LOW-PROFILE MESH PLATE
DEAN G LORICH 1, STEPHEN J WARNER, PATRICK C SCHOTTEL, ANDRE D SHAFFER, LIONEL E LAZARO, DAVID L HELFET
<HTTPS://PUBMED.NCBI.NLM.NIH.GOV/26270460/>
6. WHAT LEADS TO UNFAVOURABLE CYBEX TEST RESULTS FOR QUADRICEPS POWER AFTER MODIFIED TENSION BAND OSTEOSYNTHESIS OF PATELLAR FRACTURES?
AHMET BAYAR A, *, ERTUG˘RUL S˘ENER B , SELC˘UK KESER A , JALE MERAY C , AYKIN S˘IMS˘EK B , ALPASLAN S˘ENKO˘YLU˘ D
<HTTPS://SCI-HUB.TW/HTTPS://WWW.SCIENCEDIRECT.COM/SCIENCE/ARTICLE/ABS/PII/S0020138305004973> / DOI:10.1016/J.INJURY.2005.12.017
7. FUNCTIONAL OUTCOMES AFTER OPERATIVELY TREATED PATELLA FRACTURES.
LEBRUN CT, LANGFORD JR, SAGI HC
J ORTHOP TRAUMA. 2012 JUL; 26(7):422-6. PMID: 22183197